

Direct spectrophotometric determination of gold(III) using 2-aminoacetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2-AAINH)

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A simple, highly sensitive and specific spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of gold(III) in aqueous dimethylformamide (DMF). The metal ion reacts with 2-aminoacetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2-AAINH) forming a reddish brown complex in the pH range 3.0–6.0. The complex shows maximum absorption at 440 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.400–5.00 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $3.50 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0056 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. Job's method indicates the formation of two complex species. The stability constants corresponding to these maxima were determined and found to be 9.6×10^{15} (1 : 3, M : R) and 4.45×10^{12} (2 : 1, M : R). The method has been employed successfully for the determination of gold(III) in pharmaceutical samples.

The large molar absorptivity ($\epsilon = 3.50 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the coloured reaction indicates that the method is highly sensitive for the determination of gold(III). Number of spectrophotometric methods proposed for the determination of gold in recent times are no doubt highly sensitive. But many of them involve ternary system¹⁻⁷ or surfactant effects⁸⁻¹³ or oxidizing agents¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Some of the reported methods^{4,14,18} suffer from serious interference from foreign ions. The present paper describes a very simple, rapid, selective and sensitive and direct spectrophotometric method for the determination of micro amounts of gold in aqueous medium by complexing with 2-aminoacetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone (2-AAINH).

Results and discussion

Gold(III) reacts with 2-AAINH in acidic buffer medium forming reddish brown soluble complex. The absorption spectra of the solution containing Au^{III} -2-AAINH complex against the reagent blank and that of reagent solution against the corresponding buffer blank are recorded in the wavelength range 360–600 nm. The typical spectra are presented in Fig. 1. The coloured solution showed absorption maximum (λ_{max}) at 440 nm. The colour intensity was maximum and constant in the pH range 3.0–6.0. A ten fold molar excess of the reagent was necessary for complete and constant colour development. The colour formation was instantaneous and stable for more than 72 h.

Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 0.40–

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of (a) 2-AAINH vs buffer blank, (b) Au^{III} -2-AAINH system vs reagent blank. $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}] = 2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$; $[2\text{-AAINH}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; pH = 4.0.

$500 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of gold(III). The molar absorptivity of complex at 440 nm and at pH 4.0 was calculated as $3.50 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Sandell's sensitivity of the method was found to be $0.0056 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The standard deviation of the method for ten determinations of $1.97 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of gold(III) is ± 0.0061 . The correlation coefficient (γ) for the experimental data is 0.9999. The composition of the complex determined using Job's continuous variation method indicates the formation of two complex species. The stability constants corresponding to these maxima were determined and found to be 9.6×10^{15} (1 : 3, M : R)

and 4.45×10^{12} (2 : 1, M : R).

The effect of diverse ions in the determination of gold(III) were examined under the optimum conditions. The present method is devoid of interference from most of the anions and cations. The interference from some of the cations like Pd^{II} , V^{V} and high amounts of Fe^{III} can be successfully avoided by masking them with suitable amounts of fluoride. The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Tolerance limits of diverse ions in the determination of gold(III) pH = 4.0; amount of gold(III) = $1.97 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$

Ion	Tolerance limit $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	Ion	Tolerance limit $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$
EDTA	37	Pd^{II}	Interferes
Citrate	496	Ce^{IV}	28
Bromate	563	U^{VI}	30
Thiourea	836	Tl^{III}	36
Oxalate	968	Fe^{III}	40
			1000 ^a
Phosphate	1045	Ag^{I}	50
Iodide	1270	Cr^{III}	52
Thiosulphate	1375	W^{VI}	54
Ascorbate	1780	Th^{IV}	59
Tartrate	1800	Zr^{IV}	60
Fluoride	1900	Cu^{II}	63
Nitrate	3400	Mo^{VI}	72
Chloride	3850	Pt^{IV}	98
Sulphate	5200	Ca^{II}	110
		Mn^{II}	110
		V^{V}	110 ^a
		Cd^{II}	112
		Pb^{II}	120
		Zn^{II}	120
		Al^{III}	130
		Ni^{II}	159
		Mg^{II}	264
		Sn^{II}	295
		Ba^{II}	330

^aIn presence of $500 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of fluoride.

Application :

The present method was applied for the determination of gold(III) in pharmaceutical formulations.

Experimental

A Shimadzu UV-visible spectrophotometer Model UV-160 A equipped with 1 cm quartz cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements. The pH measurements

were made with a Phillips Digital pH meter Model PP 9046. The chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. 2-Aminoacetophenone isonicotinoyl hydrazone was prepared by condensing purified samples of 2-aminoacetophenone and isonicotinic acid hydrazide in aqueous methanol in the presence of sodium hydroxide using the general procedure¹⁹. The melting point of the product is 183–185°. The structure of the product obtained is ascertained from IR and NMR spectral studies.

The structure is as follows.

A 0.01 M solution of the reagent in dimethylformamide (DMF) was used in the present studies. Stock solution of gold(III) was prepared by dissolving 1 g of chloro auric acid (Johnson Mathay, Materials Technology, U.K.) in distilled water after adding few drops of dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution is made up to the mark in 100 ml volumetric flask. The gold content of the solution was determined by rhodamine B method¹⁷. The working solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solution to an appropriate volume. Buffer solutions are prepared by employing 1 M HCl and 1 M sodium acetate (pH 1 to 3) and 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M sodium acetate (pH 3.5 to 7.0).

To 5 ml of buffer solution (pH 4.0), 2 ml of DMF and 1 ml of 2-AAINH (1×10^{-2} M) taken in each of a set of different 10 ml volumetric flask, varying amounts of gold(III) were added and made up to the mark with doubly distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 440 nm against the reagent blank. The calibration curve was prepared by plotting the absorbance against the amount of gold(III). The calibration plot follows the equation $A = 0.1726c + 0.0061$.

Preparation of sample solution :

20 capsules of Rheumartho with gold (Sri Baidyanath Ayurvedic Bhavan Ltd., Nagpur, India) and K.K. Forte with gold (Kalpa Pharma, Vijayawada, India) are ground well and dissolved in minimum volume of conc. hydrochloric acid and evaporated to dryness. The residue is redissolved in 10 ml of conc. HCl and diluted to 50 ml. It is filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 41 and the clean solution is collected into a 100 ml standard flask. The contents are diluted to the mark with distilled water.

10 ml of this solution is further diluted to get working solutions.

Different aliquots of sample solutions are treated with 5 ml of buffer solution (pH 4.0) and 1 ml of 2-AAINH ($1 \times 10^{-2} M$) and made up to the mark in 10 ml volumetric flasks with distilled water. The absorbance of the resultant solutions is measured at 440 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of gold present in the sample solutions is computed from a pre-determined calibration plot and compared with the results obtained by Rhodamine B¹⁷. The results are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Analyses of pharmaceutical samples for gold content

Sample	Amount of gold ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)		Relative error %
	Present method	Rhodamine-B ⁵⁰	
Rheumartho with gold	1.02	1.01	-0.99
	1.82	1.84	1.08
	2.13	2.11	-0.94
	3.17	3.13	1.27
K. K. Forte with gold	0.42	0.44	4.54
	0.87	0.86	-1.16
	1.20	1.24	3.22
	2.49	2.45	-1.63

The present method is more sensitive and also highly selective than the methods reported by Prakash *et al.*²⁰, Pal *et al.*²¹, Paria *et al.*²², Amin *et al.*²³ and Kabil *et al.*¹⁸. The method is applied for the analysis of complex materials with good accuracy.

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